

Extracting machine-readable constructive element precedence from BIM models

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Abstract

Among the main causes commonly cited for delays in civil construction projects are (1) unpredictable external factors, such as weather conditions, and (2) inadequate planning involving poor resource allocation and failures in structuring precedence relationships between construction elements. The elaboration and revision of construction schedules, on the other hand, is an arduous task that involves selecting hundreds of activities, determining their durations and correct sequencing them, as well as associating tasks through the analysis of their physical, temporal, contractual characteristics, etc., and identifying numerous factors and constraints, such as construction methods and available resources, deadlines, and budget limit, among many other pieces of information that may not be readily available. Assumptions, therefore, are commonly adopted. Moreover, the dynamic aspect of civil construction, in which scope changes occur frequently, further complicates the implementation of current planning techniques throughout the project's life cycle. Thus, the need arises to automate processes, which are currently executed manually and slowly.

The implementation of the BIM methodology aimed at construction management has brought several advantages. Its use as a database, where the physical and functional characteristics of assets are stored, enables the development of more robust planning, aligned with new technologies, such as 4D BIM. Additionally, open and standardized data, known as IFC, allows access to these characteristics without the need to purchase licenses for BIM software.

This thesis presents a methodology for automatically extracting precedence relationships of construction elements from BIM models through the geometric component accessible in available open data formats and through publicly distributed IT tools and applications. This work contributes not only to automating a stage in the preparation of civil construction schedules but also paves the way for potential future work in its application to construction and demolition optimization processes.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/EhXG-u1sZUI>

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